

Q1

1. Academic Position

- PhD student/Postdoc
- Lecturer (adjunkt)/Senior Lecturer (lektor)/ Associate Senior Lecturer (BUL)
- Professor

Q2

2. Years of teaching experience in Higher Education

- [0-3)
- [3-6)
- [6-10)
- 10+

Q3

3. Do you manage a course now or have you done it in the past?

- Yes
- No

Q15

4. How long ago since you had an exam review (in months)

Q16

5. In the last 2 years how many exam reviews have you participated in

Q4

6. During your entire career how many exam reviews have you participated in?

- 0
- 1-5
- 6-10
- 11-30
- 31+

Q5

7. Do you change any grades during exam review

- All the time
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

Q20

8. In what ways have you performed a grade review?

- I have grade review hours after I publish the grade
- I do grade review offline after written request by a student
- I do group grade reviews
- I do peer to peer grade reviews
- I do one on one grade reviews
- I do external/panel grade reviews
- Other (fill what you do in the box below)

Comment

Q17

9. Approximately what percentage of your grade reviews involve a dispute or conflict

- 0%
- 1-10%
- 11-25%
- 26-50%
- >50%

Q14

10. Has any student reacted in an improper manner during the review [multiple choice]

- No, it never happened to me
- Yes, student resorted to personal insults
- Yes, student raised voice/shouted
- Yes, student refused to leave
- Yes, student became emotional distressed
- Yes, student showed physical aggression/threats
- Yes, other(fill the comment box below)

Comment

Q8

11. What are the most frequent causes for grade disputes from the student [multiple choice]

- Errors and technical issues in assessments
- Administration errors
- Misunderstanding of the student
- Misunderstanding of the question/question unclear
- Different evaluator experience
- Variable Misalignment with educational and learning goals
- Lack of clarity and transparency in grading process
- High stakes associated to the grade
- Other (fill the comment box below)

Comment

Q9

12. During the exam review, have you ever felt uncomfortable during the grade review?

- Yes
- No

Q10

13. On average, how many minutes do you spend handling a single grade dispute

Q11

14. What characteristics do the students requesting grade review present

- High-grade students / Perfectionists (questions grading because of seeking flawless grades)
- Dissatisfied students / Trust erosion (questions grading because of a perceived lack of fairness)
- Insecure (Questions the grade because of lack of knowledge)
- Strategic negotiator (Questions grading as a general strategy to improve grades, but is not a perfectionist)
- Constrained students (Questions the grade because the student were externally constrained - e.g. high load, illness, lack of time, other impairment)
- Seeking guidance (Questions grading as an opportunity to chat about other things, like knowledge, future opportunities, future collaboration, etc.)
- Cultural barrier/Language barrier (Questions the grade due to perceived cultural or language barriers, that affects their performance)
- Learning disability (Questions grading in light of a learning disability)

Q12

15. Do you think that students take the grade review seriously

- All
- Most
- Some
- Few
- None

Q18

16. Which of the following emotions do you typically feel after an exam review session

- Indifference
- Confidence/Empowerment
- Exhaustion
- Anxiety
- Satisfaction (helped students)
- Frustration
- Relief

Q19

17. I find the current grade review process

- Highly efficient
- Somewhat efficient
- Somewhat burdensome
- Highly burdensome

18. Grade review

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Grade reviews are relevant for the students	<input type="radio"/>				
Grade reviews make evaluations more fair	<input type="radio"/>				
Grade reviews helps to correct errors	<input type="radio"/>				
Students enjoy grade reviews	<input type="radio"/>				
Some students may cause discomfort to other students attending the grade review	<input type="radio"/>				
In-depth grade review discussion is beneficial for the students	<input type="radio"/>				
Grade reviews makes me stressed	<input type="radio"/>				
Students that are verbally argumentative are more likely to get a grade improvement	<input type="radio"/>				
Grade reviews disadvantage shy or quiet students	<input type="radio"/>				
The insights gained from grade reviews have led me to improve the course materials or assessments.	<input type="radio"/>				
Grade reviews makes me feel frustrated with the administration/grading rules	<input type="radio"/>				
I feel a sense of satisfaction when I resolve a grade dispute effectively	<input type="radio"/>				